

Abstract

Possible Effects of Acupuncture on Gait Symptoms of Patients with Multiple Sclerosis.

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Abstract

Background: Multiple sclerosis (MS) is a complex and heterogeneous neurological disorder. Approximately 85% of individuals with MS identify gait impairment as a primary limitation in their daily activities. While previous research has indicated that acupuncture may reduce spasticity and improve balance and fatigue, specific evidence regarding its impact on gait remains limited.

Objective: This study was designed to evaluate the clinical effects of an acupuncture protocol, based on the Heidelberg Model of Traditional Chinese Medicine (TCM), on mobility in patients with relapsing–remitting multiple sclerosis (RRMS).

Methods: The study cohort comprised 20 individuals diagnosed with RRMS presenting with gait dysfunction. Gait performance was quantitatively assessed using the Timed 25-Foot Walk (T25FW) test. The study compared the efficacy of verum (true) acupuncture against a sham control.

Results: The findings demonstrate that the T25FW is a sensitive and reliable tool for detecting clinical changes following acupuncture intervention. Statistical analysis revealed a significant reduction in the time required to complete the T25FW following verum acupuncture, whereas no significant changes were observed in the sham group. Furthermore, 95% of participants exhibited measurable improvement after true acupuncture, compared to only 45% in the sham cohort.

Conclusions: This study provides evidence that acupuncture based on the Heidelberg Model can significantly enhance mobility in MS patients. Although larger-scale trials are necessary to confirm long-term clinical applicability and cost-effectiveness, these results suggest that acupuncture is a promising therapeutic option for managing gait impairment in multiple sclerosis.

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a) True Acupuncture

a) Sham Acupuncture

Percentage of improvement for each of the patient in the T25FW. a) for true acupuncture treatment and b) for sham acupuncture treatment.

Keywords: Multiple Sclerosis; Relapsing–Remitting; Gait Impairment; Acupuncture; T25FW; Heidelberg Model of TCM.

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